

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17896539

A Systematic Review of Online Food Delivery in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges

Surajo Abba Ahmed

**Department of General Studies (Information Technology)
Sani Zangon Daura, School of Health Technology Daura, Katsina State
Katsina State College of Health Science and Technology, Nigeria
Author email : surajoabba2013@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

Online food delivery in Nigeria is witnessing intense growth , this is as a result of rising Smartphone users , increased urbanization in areas like Lagos , Abuja , Rivers , Kano and a growing feeling for conveniences services , as consumers looks for quick and accessible meal options through the internet. Online food market in Nigeria is booming, with a growth rate exceeding 20%. Method of review of related literature was conducted using previous and present data to achieve the objectives of this paper, 20 articles were selected at random that were published within (2010-2025). The paper attempted to explain an overview of online food delivery in Nigeria, trends in the markets, types of application of online food delivery in used in Nigeria and its networks, food delivery applications in Nigeria by users rating. The paper also attempts to discuss some of the technological factors that hinder online food delivery in Nigeria. The research recommends some ways to reduce these factors that hinder online food delivery in Nigeria. Overall the study suggested that food delivery in Nigeria is at its infancy stage, gradually online food delivery would dominate most cities in Nigeria with better economic and social development improvement, because of its convenience services, access to internet and rising Smartphone users.

Keywords: Online food, Delivery, Network, Application, Internet, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Online food delivery in Nigeria is booming with rising standard of living, people are looking for conveniences of food delivery apps that bring food at their doorsteps most of the time through the use of phone apps and internet. According to (Novatia, 2024) says that consumers play a significant role in making this transformation by choosing online platform over traditional dining services.

Computers, internet services, Smartphone, tablet, mobile applications have seriously altered daily livelihood, among other information technologies. the influence of online services give more option to working class to buy food online rather than dine out and also save time for those who don't have time to cook. The online food ordering platform provides direct and efficient services to many customers and restaurants to send online order to restaurant, and deliver takeaway to customers (Xu, 2019).

The increased number of e-food delivery, app are coming up very fast, food delivery application are becoming more and more popular among Nigerians' as a quick and straightforward way to get food on the table. These applications allow customers to view listed restaurants, menus, and rating, places and verify order using online payment, and track order progress without physically or over the phone interacting with the restaurants (P. Kaur, 2020).

According to a report by IMARC (2024) online food delivery refers to process of ordering and delivering food through online portals. It comprises an order management system that streamlines the entire ordering

process, starting from order placement to final delivery. It relies on mobile base software, application, and website that offer access to numerous food joints based on the preference of customer. It enable eateries to take the placed order, prepare the particular dish on time and hand it to over to the delivery personal to deliver it to the buyer. It also allows customers to provide valuable reviews about the service and quality of food offered by the restaurant on the online portal.

The main objectives of the study is to identify the types of application online food deliveries make use of in Nigeria, the reliable network that facilitate online food delivery in Nigeria, and also to look into the technological aspects that limit online food delivery in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online food delivery in Nigeria is witnessing rapid growth, the food industry is completely changing and transforming due to the application of technology and also impacting the customers and business alike. This growth or rather transformation is as a result of Smartphone penetration among youth, internet access and change in life style because youth now value convenience and speed.

According to report by IMARC (2024) the report has provided a detailed breakup and analysis of Nigeria online food delivery, which are categorized based on the platform type. This includes mobile application users and website users. According to their report mobile application users represent the largest segment. However in another statement made by IMARC (2024) a detailed breakup and analysis of Nigerian online food delivery based on payment mode was investigated. These include online cash payment or cash on delivery payment. According to the report by IMARC (2024), online cash payment accounted for the largest share.

Similarly IMARC (2024) a detailed breakup and analysis of Nigerian online food delivery market based on end users was also investigated. The analysis involves individual order or corporate order, according to the report individual order accounted for the largest market share.

Moreover in a statement made by IMARC (2024) a detailed breakup and analysis of Nigerian online food delivery market based on regional market. According a comprehensive analysis of all the major regional market was made, these include North West, South West, and North central and other. According to the report North West was the largest market for online food delivery in Nigeria. some of the factor driving north west online food delivery in Nigeria is attributed to growing popularity of ordering online food , increasing consumption of fast food , rising number of quick service restaurant and cafes.

An overview of online food delivery in Nigeria

Online food delivery refers to the process where consumers order food from restaurants or food vendors through digital platforms like websites or mobiles apps, and have it delivered to their location. This service has gained significant attraction due to its conveniences and accessibility, offering users the ability to order food from various establishments with a few tabs on their devices (Sudra, 2020).

Online platform provide easy access to wide variety of cuisines from the comfort of their home or office. They save time and effort, allowing people to browse menus, compare options, and place order with just a few tabs on their Smartphone (Sudra, 2020).

Trend in the market

Online food delivery industries is experiencing rapid growth , fueled by increased usage of Smartphone and internet penetration , busy life style , and lasting impact of the Covid pandemic.

in Nigeria a major factor that bust online food delivery are macroeconomics factors such as urbanization , disposable income levels, and changing consumer behavior

According to Blond (2024) there are certain major factors that lead to trends of online food delivery in 2025.

1. Tech Giant Entering into The Market: when Amazon acquired whole foods in 2017. Then afterward Uber lunched its food delivery platform named Ubereats.
2. Direct Restaurant Delivery: the trend of delivering food directly to user without involving third party is also making online food delivery more appealing to customers.

3. Drone Delivery: online food delivery by drones is one of the most admired trends, since 2012 many firms have taken the initiative to deliver meal to their customers via a drone. Domino delivered pizza to its customer in 2016 in New Zealand via drone.
4. Robot Delivery: the meal industry delivery is not only limited to use of drone, but industries are applying AI and robotics engineering in delivering meals to its customers.
5. Virtual Kitchens: virtual kitchens are also known as cloud kitchens that only produce delivery, only meals. These are also one of the profitable trends in food delivery in 2025. All you need is enough area for setting up your kitchen without any dining space.

Types of Application of Online Food Delivery in used in Nigeria and its Networks

In Nigeria, online food delivery application offer various services, primarily categorized as on- demand food delivery and restaurant-specific platforms. Key players include Jumia food, Bolt Food, Chowdeck, and Glovo, among others leveraging diverse networks for delivery.

Types of application:

1. On-demand food delivery apps:

These apps act as intermediaries, connecting users with wide range of restaurants and food vendors. Example includes Jumia Food, Bolt Food , Chowdeck and Glovo.

2. Restaurant –specific App/Websites:

Some restaurant may have their own apps or websites for online ordering and delivery, offering a more focused selection and potentially unique menus items.

Networks Used

1. Proprietary Delivery Network:

Some services, like Jumia Food and Bolt Food, utilize their own delivery networks, often employing a combination of motor cycle , cars and other vehicles .

2. Third party Delivery Services

Others may integrate with third- party delivery companies like Gokada or Kwik Delivery to handle the logistics of getting food to costumers.

3. Restaurant –Owned Networks:

Restaurant with their own apps may use their own delivery personnel or partner with specific delivery services.

Key players include:

- a) Jumia Food : A leading platform offering wide selection of restaurants cuisine across major cities in Nigeria
- b) Bolt Food : A popular option known for its quick and reliable service, offering various restaurants and meal choices
- c) Chowdeck: A combinatory-backed platform gaining traction in Lagos and other major cities.
- d) Glovo: A delivery service that handle food delivery in Nigeria and other region.
- e) Konga Food : another major player in online food delivery in Nigeria
- f) Gokada Food: A platform that provide on-demand food service delivery in Nigeria .
- g) OyaNow Food: A delivery service that focuses on conveniences and speed
- h) Eden Life: An online food delivery service that offers a variety of meal option.

Food Delivery Applications in Nigeria by Users Rating.

According to a report by Ozibo (2025) stated that several food delivery application are available in Nigeria and their user rating vary some of top-rated apps include Chowdeck, Glovo, and FoodCourt, with rating around 4.0 and above, other popular options with good user rating include Foodelo, Bolt Food, MANO, Heyfood, and UrbanEats.

Some detailed look at some of the apps and their user ratings according to Ozibo (2025):

- a) **Chowdeck:** Has a user rating of 4.5
- b) **Glovo:** Also holds a 4.5 rating
- c) **FoodCourt:** Features a 4.3 rating

- d) **Foodelo:** Boasts a 4.5 user rating,
- e) **Bolt Food:** Maintains a 4.2 rating,
- f) **MANO:** Has a user rating of 4.2.
- g) **Heyfood:** Also has a 4.2 user rating.
- h) **UrbanEats:** Has a user rating of 4.0.

Other apps like Jumia Food are also popular in Nigeria but their user rating may vary

Technological factors that limit online food delivery in Nigeria

Among many factors that affects online food delivery in Nigeria, there are several of them including infrastructural deficits, high cost, prices sensitivity and logistical challenges , but this research is focusing on technological aspect that hinder online food delivery in Nigeria, according to report by Alda (2025):

1. Limited internet access: in some areas, limited internet access or lack of Smartphone can restrict access to online food delivery platform.
2. Digital literacy: some user may lack the digital skills to navigate online platforms.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employ in these research work involve the analysis of existing literature review. The research make used of 20 published articles that were selected at random from the year (2010-2025),using previous and existing literature reviews to obtain information and understand the current state of online food delivery in Nigeria and also to developed recommendations for improvement. A comprehensive review of previous and existing literature in online food delivery in Nigeria was conducted to understand the application and mode of operandi of online food delivery and be able to identify gaps that exist for improvement. This research was able to examine the technological knowhow, the applications and networks use by online food delivery, procedure for operation and approach, and also study publications by experts on online food delivery in Nigeria. Through this analysis the researcher was able to identify some of the key challenges faced by these marketers in Nigeria and make recommendations.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

From the far gone discussion made, no doubt online food delivery in Nigeria is facing profound challenges which if neglected will eventually lead to the downfall of the entire system. Therefore the following findings focus on technological aspect of food delivery in Nigeria, the following findings were made:

1. Online food delivery in Nigeria is facing unstable economics factors, Nigeria inflation rate has risen prices of food stuff has risen couple with price of diesel and petrol. These factor have contributed to many online food delivery to be out of work or they have increase their price of rendering business these has greatly reduced their customers.
2. Some key factors that influence online delivery in Nigeria are demographic changes among young, technological innovations and social changes all these factors drive the rapid growth of food business in online food delivery in Nigeria.
3. Payments options and customer service: lack of convenient and secure payment options , such as limited availability of online payment gateways or concern about card security this finding is in agreement with the findings of (Folorunso, October 2006)
4. Most online food deliveries do not make use of user-friendly mobile app: a well designed mobile app and easy to navigate apps are essential for attracting and retaining customer. These apps allow users to browse menus, place order, track deliveries, and make payment.
5. Online food delivery in Nigeria are lagging behind in the use of GPS Tracking device , customers most often depend on telephone communication for food delivery services which is not reliable and consume a lot of money while GPS technology allow both customers and delivery

personal to track the location of the delivery enhancing transparency and accountability , these finding is in agreement with the finding of .

6. The use of social media is paramount in online food delivery in Nigeria for marketing and customer engagement toward drawing the attention of the customer.
7. There are still region in Nigeria were they are still facing limited internet access , despite growing internet access in Nigeria there still area were internet access is still limited , these find is in agreement with the finding of (Tagrul Daim, January 2013) that access to internet in some part of the country is still limited.
8. The researcher was able to identify security concern among customers, using online transactions customers are skeptical about the safety of online delivery platform how safe and secure is the transaction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Online food delivery in Nigeria can be improved through government intervention by improving standard of living through better wages, and reducing economic hardship to its citizen.
2. Online payment medium should be highly secured to prevent any unauthorized access to customers account; the account of the customer should be highly secured.
3. To enhance online food delivery in Nigeria, designers of the application (programmers) should focus on user friendliness making it easy buy, make choice, preferred selection, and alternative to choice while maintaining integrity and security.
4. To draw the attention of customer, online food vendors should utilized social media application through marketing strategies for optimal gain.
5. To facilitate online food delivery in Nigeria there is need for the vendors to collaborate with network providers to increased network coverage in areas where there is still limited internet access.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and findings of the research work, it was concluded that online food delivery market is a booming business in Nigeria, they are making a lot of profit based on a report by Statista (2025) that revenue in online food delivery market is projected to reached US\$ 3.07bn in 2025 and also revenue generation is expected to show an annual growth rate of (AGR 2025-2030) of 10.05% resulting in a projected market volume of US\$ 4.95bn by 2030 ,despite the success recorded, Nigeria online food delivery is facing hard time with unstable economics factor, Nigeria is witnessing high inflation rate that lead to the decline in online food delivery. Another major obstacle faced by customers of online services delivery is the issue of security concern before and after transaction, GPS tracking devices, non application of user friendly app that guide customer to make informed decision. However this research work limitation is to explore the online food delivery applications, how they work and how user friendliness is. These are some of the gray area that needs further research.

REFERENCES

- Adomim, E. E. (2010). Application of ICTs in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *Library Philosophy and Practice* , 3-19.
- Agboeze, M. U. (2012). Utilization of e-learning technology resources in accounting education instructional delivert methods in Nigeria universities. *international journal of education research* , 26-38.
- Ajisafe, O. (2014). Fostering utilization of information and communication technology skills among students of Business Education of Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research* , 171-174.
- Alda, M. (2025). *Online Food Delivery - Nigeria*. New York, USA: Statista.
- Atureta. (2011). Reviewing the benefits of ICTs in the Nigerian education system.

- Ayeni, A. J., & Ogunbamera, M. (2013). effective utilization and maintenance of ICT facilities for quality teaching and learning outcome in secondary schools in Ondo state , Nigeria. *international journal of research studies in educational technology* , vol 2, number 2, 27-40.
- Blond, A. (2024, Nov 08). 10 Food Delivery Industry Trends for 2025. 10926 David Taylor Dr STE 120, Charlotte, NC 28262, United State.
- Deeboom, M. T., & Zite, B. N. (2016). Effectiveness of information Communication Tech. (ICT) in Teaching and learning in Public Senior Secondary School in Ogoni Area , River State. *international journal of education and evaluation* , ISSN 2489-0073 Vol.2 No4.
- Drummond, J., Bowen, T.-J., & Hall, A.-N. (2013, 4 24). *Weebly*. Retrieved 12 04, 2022, from Weebly: <http://publicissuescomp1220uwi.weebly.com/index.html>
- Education, F. M. (2010). *State of Education in Nigeria*. Federal Capital Territory , Abuja: Beyond Access.
- Elizabeth, O. (2021). *Explainer: What You Need To Know About Bimodal Voter Accreditation System* . Lagos: Sahara Reportes Newspaper.
- Folorunso, O. . (October 2006). Factor Affeting the Adoption of E-Commerce: A study in Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences* 6(10) .
- Garrett, M. G. (2020). *12 cyber threat that could wreak havoc on the election*. Newyork: Wired.
- H., S. (2007). *Social network lunches worldwide spam Campaigns*. New York Times.
- Ibrahim, U. (2019). impact of Cybercrime on the Nigerian Economy and the Banking System. *NDIC-Quarterly* , 4.
- imarc. (2024). *Nigeria Online Food Delivery Market Report by Platform Type (Mobile Applications, Websites), Business Model (Order Focused Food Delivery System, Logistics Based Food Delivery System, Full-Service Food Delivery System), Payment Mode (Online, Cash on Delive*. 134 N 4th St. Brooklyn, NY 11249, USA: IMARC Group.
- Inwalomhe, D. (2022). *Hackers and electronic transmission of elections result*. Lagos: Punch Newspapers.
- Jamie, I. (Feb 2025). Strengthening Cyber Resilience in Nigeria’s Public. *Mengkorn-Pum* .
- Kaplan, B. J. (2015). Theory of deterrence and individual behavior. Can lawsuits control file be sharing on the Internet? *Review of Law and & Economics* 3 (3) , 693-714.
- Mary Mojirade Ayantunji, A. E. (2024). STRENGTHENING CYBERSECURITY IN NIGERIA: A HOLISTIC APPROACH. *Scientific and Practical Cyber Security Journal (SPCSJ)* 8(2): 51 – 58 ISSN 2587-4667 *Scientific* , 55.
- Meriam, I. (2022). *2023 INEC deploying technology to ensure Nigeras votes count*. Abuja: Premium Times newspaper.
- Novatia. (2024). *Online Food Delivery Service Feasibility Study Services in Nigeria | Novatia Consulting*. 4th Floor, Suite 3AB, No 34/36 Ikorodu Road,: Novatia Consulting.
- Ogala, E. (2015). *How PREMIUM TIMES survived massive cyber attacks during presidential election coverage*. Abuja: Premium Times Newspaper.
- oyewole, F. F. (2024). *Curb Cybercrime*. Washington: Forbes.
- Ozibo, R. (2025). *Top 8 food delivery apps in Nigeria by user rating as of March 2025*. Lagos: Nairametrics.
- P. Kaur, A. D. (2020). Innovation resistance theory perspective on the use of food delivery applications. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 34 (6) , 1746-1768.
- Ron, R., Victoria, P., Richard, G., Deborah, B., & Rosalie, M. (2021, December 05). Cyber Resiliency and innovative. *Developing Cyber-Resilient Systems: A System Security Engineering Approach* , pp. NIST Special Publication 800-160, Volume 2.
- Samuel, O. (2023). *Cybersecurity Risks and Countermeasures in Nigeria*. Lagos: Vast Thinking Tech Ltd.
- Sasu, D. D. (2024). *Internet users in Nigeria 2018-2022, with forecasts up until 2027*. Germany: Statista.

- Schneier, D. &. (2016, November). *Lessons From the Dyn DDoS Attack*. Retrieved May 13, 2025, from Schneier on Security Blog.: https://www.schneier.com/blog/archives/2016/11/lessons_from_th_5.html
- Statista. (2025). *Online food delivery in Nigeria*. New York , United State: Statista.
- Stuart, J. (2019). *Protecting Elections from cyberattack* . Washington DC: The Olive Branch.
- Sudra, A. (2020, Feb 28). *Explained Advantages and Process of Online Food Delivery System*. Retrieved July 2025, 13, from Deonae: <https://deonde.co/blog/explained-advantages-and-process-of-online-food-delivery-system>
- Tagrul Daim, N. B. (January 2013). Exploring Technology Acceptance for Online food Services. *Journal of Business Information System* 12(4): , 383-403.
- Tinio, V. L. (2002). ICT in Education. *UN development programme* , 4-23.
- Ufuoma, V. (2022). *Hackers attacked our result portal during Ekiti, Osun election*. Ibadan: ICIR Newspaper.
- Ugwoke, E. O. (2011). Effective Utilization of ICT for repositioning Business education program in tertiary institutions in Nigeria for national development. *International Journal of Education Research* , vol 11(1), 202-214.
- Xu, X. &. (2019). Restaurant information cues, Diners' expectation, and need for cognition:Experimental studies of online -to -offline mobile food ordering . *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*,51 , 231-241.
- Z., K. P. (2007). The imperative of information and communication technologies for teachers in Nigeria higher education . *journal of online learning and teaching* , 3(4).